

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESSES OF FURANO COMPOUNDS:
PART XIV. ACYLATION OF 2- AND 3- SUBSTITUTED
BENZOFURANS

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Acylation of benzofurans, substituted by alkyl or aryl groups in 2- and 3-positions, has been examined and it is shown that the benzofurans, substituted in 2-position, are acylated in 3- position and *vice versa*. Formylation of 2-benzylcoumarone has given a formyl- β brazan. Alternative methods of synthesis of α - and β -brazans have been described.

Substitution reactions of benzofurans have been studied extensively by several workers (Stoermer *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2094; 1902, 35, 1633; 1909, 42, 199; *Annalen*, 1900, 312, 237; Smith, *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, 32, 2938; Adams and Rindfusz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 648; Robertson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 921; 1938, 306; 1949, 2057 etc.) and an excellent summarised account may be found in "Heterocyclic Compounds" (Elderfield and Meyer, Vol. 2, p., 17, Wiley, New York). During the synthesis of various condensed benzofurans, it was intended to study the course of substitutions of benzofurans having alkyl or aryl groups in 2- and 3- positions and, for this purpose, studies on acylation of benzofurans by the Friedel-Crafts reaction (Smith, *loc. cit.*) or formylation by dimethylformamide were undertaken. This work was, however, anticipated by a recent publication of Buu-Hoï *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3688) and so the part of the results, not covered by these workers, is reported herein.

Acylation of 2-Substituted Benzofurans.—Acetylation of 2-methylcoumarone by acetyl chloride and stannic chloride afforded an excellent yield of 2-methyl-3-acetylcoumarone. The orientation was established by oxidising the product with sodium hypobromite to the known 2-methylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (cf. Part XII, this *Journal* 1957, 34, 299). 2-Benzylcoumarone (Stoermer *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 72) was similarly acylated in excellent yield to 3-acetyl-2-benzylcoumarone (Buu Hoï *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3693). This compound was orientated by oxidising it with sodium hypobromite to 2-benzylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (I) which was cyclised to 11-hydroxy- β -brazan and then converted into β -brazanquinone. 2-Phenylcoumarone (and its derivatives) was similarly converted into acetyl derivative and oriented.

(I)

(II)

Formylation of 2-phenylcoumarone with dimethylformamide and phosphorus oxychloride gave an excellent yield of 3 formyl-2-phenylcoumarone, orientation of which was established by oxidising it with potassium permanganate in acetone to

2-phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 175, 447). The aldehyde was converted into the α -ketonic acid (II) via the corresponding azlactone and then into α -brazan by hydrobromic acid in acetic acid, the decarboxylation having taken place before cyclisation.

Formylation of 2-benzylcoumarone gave an unexpected result. An aldehyde was obtained in poor yield and analysed for $C_{17}H_{10}O_2$, indicating introduction of two formyl groups and elimination of a molecule of water. On oxidation this aldehyde gave an acid, $C_{17}H_{10}O_3$, which furnished β -brazan on decarboxylation. The aldehyde is therefore a formyl- β -brazan which itself could not be obtained on formylation of β -brazan. On reduction by the Wolff-Kishner method, the aldehyde was converted into a methyl- β -brazan, not identical with either of the known 7- or 10-methyl- β -brazan and also proved different from 2-, 8- and 9-methyl- β -brazans which were synthesised for the purpose. As this β -brazan does not afford the corresponding quinone on oxidation with chromic acid, it appears likely that the methyl group is at the 11-position. In an attempt to settle this orientation, the cyclodehydration of 3-acetyl-2-benzylcoumarone to 11-methyl- β -brazan (III) was tried by a variety of reagents, but to no success. The difficulty in cyclising 2-acetyl-3-benzylcoumarone may be recalled in this connection (Chatterjea and Roy, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 155).

The synthesis of the above mentioned 9-methyl compound was carried out from 2-*p*-toluoylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid by ring-closure to 9-methyl- β -brazanquinone followed by reduction (cf. Chatterjea, *ibid.*, 1944, 31, 101). The cyclisation of 2-*m*-toluoylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (IV) afforded a mixture of 8- and 10-methyl- β -brazanquinones which were collectively reduced and then separated into 8-methyl- and the known 10-methyl- β -brazan. 2-Methyl- β -brazan was prepared from 2-methyldibenzofuran which on succinoylation gave a mixture of γ -ketonic acids of which the preponderating isomer must be (V). This was followed by reduction to the corresponding butyric acid, cyclisation, reduction of the resulting ketone, dehydration and dehydrogenation to 2-methyl- β -brazan. The orientation of the methyl group in this compound is open to question.

Acylation of 3-Substituted Benzofurans.—The formylation of 3-benzylcoumarone with dimethylformamide, on the other hand, gave an excellent yield of the difficultly accessible 2-formyl-3-benzylcoumarone (Chatterjea and Roy, *loc. cit.*). Similarly, 6-methoxy-3-benzyl- and 6-methoxy-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumarone gave excellent yields of the corresponding 2-formyl derivatives. In the like manner, the Friedel-Crafts acylation of 6-methoxy-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumarone with acetyl, phenylacetyl, propionyl or benzoyl chloride afforded the corresponding 2-acyl derivatives which were valuable intermediates in β -brazan synthesis (Chatterjea, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 1).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 253-54°. (Found: N, 16.0. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5N_4$ requires N, 15.8%).

The *oxime* crystallised from methyl alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 96°. (Found: C, 70.3; H, 5.6. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 69.8; H, 5.8%).

2-Methylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid was obtained in nearly quantitative yield by oxidising the above ketone (in dioxan) with sodium hypobromite at 70° for 1 hour. After destroying the unchanged hypobromite with SO₂, the mixture on acidification furnished the acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 191°

3-Acetyl-2-benzylcoumarone was prepared as above with the aid of stannic chloride. The hard complex was decomposed with water-ether, the ethereal layer washed and distilled. The acetyl compound was obtained as a yellowish viscous liquid, b.p. 190°/2 mm. (Buu Hoi *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3693 record b. p. 229-30°/18 mm). (Found: C, 81.9; H, 5.7. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{14}O_2$: C, 81.7; H, 5.6%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from acetic acid in orange-red plates, m.p. 167°. (Found: N, 12.8. $C_{23}H_{18}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.0%).

On oxidation with sodium hypobromite at 70° in dioxan solution for 1½ hours, *2-benzylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid* was obtained (yield 20-25%) which crystallised from acetic acid in prisms, m.p. 188°. (Found: C, 75.5; H, 4.5. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.8%). The compound imparted a violet-pink colour to H₂SO₄.

Cyclisation of 2-Benzylcoumarone-3-carboxylic Acid.—The acid (0.2 g.) was converted into the acid chloride by boiling with thionyl chloride (1 c.c.) in presence of a trace of pyridine for 1 hour. After removing thionyl chloride, the oily acid chloride was dissolved in pure CS₂ (3 c.c.), cooled and treated with AlCl₃ (0.6 g.) and left overnight. The aluminium complex was decomposed with iced HCl and the product (contaminated with sulphur compounds), which dissolved in alkali with violet fluorescence, was converted into β-brazaquinone, m.p. and mixed m.p. 245°, by oxidising the crude product with chromic acid (0.3 g.) in acetic acid (2 c.c.) for 2 minutes. (Found: C, 77.3; H, 3.3. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{10}O_2$: C, 77.4; H, 3.2%).

3-Acetyl-2-phenylcoumarone was prepared from 2-phenylcoumarone as above. The ketone, obtained as an oil, was identified by its *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone*, m.p. 210°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen (Chatterjea, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 175).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* of *3-acetyl-2-p-chlorophenylcoumarone* (Chatterjea and Roy, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 98), prepared similarly, crystallised from acetic acid in red plates, m.p. 210-11°. (Found: N, 12.6. $C_{22}H_{15}O_5N_4Cl$ requires N, 12.4%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* of *3-acetyl-2-p-tolylcoumarone* (Chatterjea and Roy, *loc. cit.*) crystallised from acetic acid in orange leaflets, m.p. 209°. (Found: N, 12.8. $C_{23}H_{18}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.0%).

3-Formyl-2-phenylcoumarone.—A mixture of 2-phenylcoumarone (1.0 g.), dimethylformamide (0.45 g.) and POCl₃ (0.9 g.) was heated on a boiling water-bath for 8 hours and then the mixture was cooled and carefully decomposed with alkali. The aldehyde separated as a colorless oil which solidified immediately (1.0 g.) and obtained

in prismatic needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 74-75°. (Found: C, 81.3; H, 4.4. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 81.1; H, 4.5%). The compound is fairly soluble in alcohol, and develops a greenish yellow coloration with H_2SO_4 . The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from a large volume of acetic acid in orange-red leaflets, m.p. 285° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.3. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_4$ requires N, 13.9%). The oxime, prepared in pyridine, was obtained in colorless crystalline mass from dilute alcohol, m.p. 144-45°. (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N$ requires N, 5.9%).

Oxidation of the aldehyde with $KMnO_4$ in acetone at 45° afforded a small yield of 2-phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid, identical with an authentic specimen.

Dehydration of the above mentioned oxime (0.3 g.) by boiling with acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) for 3 hours gave a small yield of 3-cyano-2-phenylcoumarone, m.p. and mixed m.p. 80-82°. (Found: N, 6.4. Calc. for $C_{13}H_9ON$: N, 6.4%).

α-Brazan from 3-formyl-2-phenylcoumarone.—A mixture of the aldehyde (2.2 g.), hippuric acid (2 g.), sodium acetate (1.0 g.) and acetic anhydride (21 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour. The azlactone gradually separated in yellow needles. Alcohol (40 c.c., 50%) was added to the mixture; the product (1.8 g.) was collected and crystallised from benzene in bright yellow plates, m.p. 225-26°. (Found: N, 3.8. $C_{21}H_{18}O_3N$ requires N, 3.8%).

Hydrolysis.—The azlactone (1.5 g.) was boiled with a mixture of sodium hydroxide (20 c.c., 10%) and alcohol (6 c.c.) for 24 hours. The mixture was diluted with water (15 c.c.), saturated with SO_2 and 2-phenylcoumarone-3-pyruvic acid (II) isolated in the usual way and obtained in yellowish prisms from acetic acid, m.p. 170°. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 4.6. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.3%). The compound develops a greenish colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. On oxidation with alkaline hydrogen peroxide at 5°, this pyruvic acid gave a good yield of 2-phenylcoumarone-3-acetic acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 142°. (Found: C, 76.1; H, 4.7. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$: C, 76.2; H, 4.8%).

Cyclisation.—A mixture of the above pyruvic acid (0.2 g.), acetic acid (3 c.c.) and hydrobromic acid (2 c.c., 48%) was boiled under reflux for 5 hours. The changes in colour of the mixture was: pink → light blue → bluish green → brown → pinkish brown. The oil that separated was taken up in ether after dilution and distilled in vacuum. *α*-Brazan quickly solidified and obtained in prismatic needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 103°. (Found: C, 87.7; H, 4.7. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{10}O$: C, 88.1; H, 4.6%).

Formylation of 2-Benzylcoumarone.—A mixture of 2-benzylcoumarone (7 g.), dimethylformamide (5 g.) and $POCl_3$ (8 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 10 hours. In the beginning there were two layers but after a few hours the mixture became homogeneous. The whole was cooled, made strongly alkaline, extracted with ether and distilled. After a fore-run of unchanged material (b.p. 140°/0.3 mm) the residual dark high-boiling material was dissolved in alcohol and left in the refrigerator. Formyl-*β*-brazan was obtained as cream-coloured needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 167°, developing orange coloration with H_2SO_4 . (Found: C, 82.6; H, 4.4. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 82.9; H, 4.1%). The oxime, prepared in pyridine, crystallised from alcohol in colorless prisms,

m.p. 232°. (Found: C, 78.3; H, 4.6. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 78.2; H, 4.2%). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. > 290°. (Found: N, 14.0. $C_{23}H_{14}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.1%).

On oxidation with a solution of potassium permanganate (0.3 g.) in water (4 c.c.) at 40°, this aldehyde (0.1 g.) furnished, in the usual way, the corresponding *carboxylic acid*, m.p. 260°, developing a yellowish colour with H_2SO_4 . (Found: C, 77.1; H, 4.0. $C_{17}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 77.8; H, 3.8%). On distillation with lime, this acid gave β -brazan in a pure condition, m.p. and mixed m.p. 207°.

Reduction of the Aldehyde.—A mixture of the aldehyde (0.5 g.), hydrazine hydrate (1 c.c., 80%) and diethyleneglycol (5 c.c.) was boiled under reflux for 3 hours, cooled, potassium hydroxide (1 g.) added and water removed from the system by distillation. The temperature of the mixture was raised to 210° and kept at this temperature for 3 hours. The *methyl- β -brazan* was isolated with ether and obtained in colorless needles from alcohol (0.35 g.), m.p. 91°; mixed m.p. with 10-methyl- β -brazan (m.p. 91°) was 65-70°. (Found: C, 87.5; H, 5.3. $C_{17}H_{12}O$ requires C, 87.9; H, 5.2%). The compound developed a yellow coloration with H_2SO_4 , turning greenish on keeping. The *picrate*, prepared in alcohol, crystallised from alcohol, containing picric acid, in orange needles, m.p. 92° (with previous sintering). (Found: N, 9.7. $C_{17}H_{12}O.C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N, 9.1 %).

9-Methyl- β -brazan.—Coumaran-dione (0.75 g.) was condensed with *p*-methylphenacyl bromide (1.1 g.) in alcoholic sodium ethoxide (sodium 0.12 g. and alcohol 12 c.c.). The resulting *ethyl 2-p-toluoylcoumarone-3-carboxylate* (0.7 g.) was obtained in colorless prisms or plates, m.p. 144° from alcohol. (Found: C, 74.1; H, 5.3. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.0; H, 5.2%). The compound showed an orange colour with H_2SO_4 . On hydrolysis with aqueous alcoholic sodium hydroxide, *p-toluoylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid* was obtained (purified through the crystalline sodium salt), crystallising from benzene-petroleum ether in colorless prisms, m.p. 150°. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 4.5. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.3%). On cyclisation through the acid chloride in the usual manner (this *Journal*, 1954, 32, 101), *9-methyl- β -brazanquinone* was obtained (yield 90%), crystallising from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 225°. (Found: C, 77.6; H, 3.7. $C_{17}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 77.8; H, 3.8 %). On boiling for 5 hours with hydriodic acid, this quinone gave *9-methyl- β -brazan*, crystallising from benzene-alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 180-81°. (Found: C, 87.5; H, 5.3. $C_{17}H_{12}O$ requires C, 87.9; H, 5.2 %).

8-Methyl- β -brazan.—*m*-Methylacetophenone was prepared from *m*-toluic acid by interaction of the acid chloride with magnesiummalonic ester (Walker and Hauser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1386), yield 60%. Bromination of the ketone in chloroform solution gave a quantitative yield of *m*-methylphenacyl bromide, b.p. 120-22°/1.5 mm. (Found: Br, 36.8. Calc. for C_9H_9OBr : Br, 37.6%). On interaction with coumaran-dione in the usual way, *ethyl m-toluoylcoumarone-3-carboxylate* was obtained, crystallising from alcohol in prisms, m.p. 103°, which on hydrolysis gave the corresponding *acid*, crystallising from benzene-petroleum ether in prismatic needles, m.p. 123-24°. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 4.5. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.3%).

On cyclisation through the acid chloride, a mixture of isomeric brazanquinones, m.p. 190-220°, was obtained in good yield. The mixture was then reduced with boiling hydriodic acid for 4 hours, when a mixture of 8- and 10-methyl- β -brazans was obtained. The mixture was separated fractionally from alcohol, when the less soluble 8-methyl- β -brazan was obtained as colorless plates, m.p. 207-208°. (Found: C, 87.4; H, 5.4. $C_{17}H_{12}O$ requires C, 87.9; H, 5.2 %). The mother-liquor on working up gave 10-methyl- β -brazan as colorless plates, m.p. and mixed m.p. 89-92°.

2-Methyl- β -brazan.—Dibenzofuran was recovered unchanged on attempted formylation with dimethylformamide. On formylation with zinc cyanide and hydrogen chloride (Adams *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2373; 1924, **46**, 1518) a moderate yield of 2-formyldibenzofuran (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 779) was obtained.

A solution of the formyl compound (6 g.) and hydrazine hydrate (3 c.c., 90%) in diethyleneglycol (30 c.c.) was boiled and then KOH (4.0 g.) was added; the mixture was refluxed for 4 hours with the removal of water and the reduced material. The distillate and the residue were extracted with ether after dilution, dried, solvent removed and 2-methyldibenzofuran distilled. The compound was obtained as a colorless liquid (1.7 g.), b.p. 215°/80 mm, which solidified, m.p. 45° (Mayer and Krieger, *Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 1695, reported b.p. 215°/0.9 mm and m.p. 45°).

A mixture of 2-methyldibenzofuran (1.5 g.), tetrachloroethane (8 c.c.), nitrobenzene (2 c.c.) and succinic anhydride (1.3 g.) was cooled to 0° and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) was added with constant shaking. The brownish solution was left in the refrigerator for 3 days and then carefully decomposed with iced hydrochloric acid. Solvent was then removed in a current of steam and the residue on boiling with a mixture of acetic acid and ethyl acetate gave a crystalline mass (1.3 g.), m.p. 155° (clearing at 180°). This was fractionally crystallised from acetic acid when two products were obtained: (i) Compound, m.p. 236-37° (1.0 g.), presumably β -[8-(2-methyldibenzofuroyl)]-propionic acid (V). (Found: C, 72.0; H, 5.3. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.4; H, 5.0 %). (ii) Compound, m.p. 159-60° (0.15 g.), probably β -[3-(2-methyldibenzofuroyl)]-propionic acid. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 5.1. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.4; H, 5.0 %).

The ketonic acid (V) on reduction by Huang-Minlon's method, afforded the corresponding *butyric acid* which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in colorless prisms, m.p. 79-80°. (Found: C, 76.0; H, 6.2. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 76.1; H, 6.0 %).

Cyclisation.—The butyric acid (0.3 g.) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (10 c.c., 90%) at the room temperature and after 12 minutes the mixture poured into water, extracted with ether, washed with alkali and the solvent evaporated, affording 2-methyl-7-keto-7:8:9:10-tetrahydro- β -brazan which crystallised from alcohol in thick plates, m.p. 159°. (Found: C, 81.3; H, 5.8. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 81.6; H, 5.6 %). The *oxime* crystallised from alcohol in cream-coloured plates, m.p. 257-58° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.1. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2N$ requires N, 5.3 %).

The above ketone (0.1 g.) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride (30 mg.) in ether (6 c.c.) at the room temperature for 20 minutes and then worked up to provide a crystalline carbinol which was mixed with palladised charcoal (20 mg.) and heated in a metal bath at 280°-300° for 2 hours. On working up, 2-methyl- β -brazan was obtained

which crystallised from alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 160°. (Found: C, 87.5; H, 5.3. $C_{17}H_{12}O$ requires C, 87.9; H, 5.2 %).

Formylation of 3-Benzylcoumarone.—Molecular quantities of the coumarone, dimethylformamide and phosphorus oxychloride were heated on the water-bath for 7 hours, left overnight and worked up as usual to furnish the 2-formyl derivative as a yellowish liquid (yield of the crude product, 90%). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in orange-red needles, m.p. 244-46°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen (Chatterjea and Roy, *loc.cit.*, p. 155). (Found: N, 13.8. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{16}O_2N_4$: N, 13.5 %).

2-Formyl-3-benzyl-6-methoxycoumarone.—6-Methoxy-3-benzylcoumarone on formylation with dimethylformamide for 2½ hours gave the 2-formyl derivative in quantitative yield. The product crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 107°.

2-Acetyl-3-benzyl-6-methoxycoumarone.—6-Methoxy-3-benzylcoumarone was acetylated in the cold as before with acetyl chloride and stannic chloride. The crude *ketone*, obtained as a semi-solid mass, gave a crystalline 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, crystallising from acetic acid in orange-red leaflets, m.p. 245°. (Found: N, 12.0. $C_{24}H_{20}O_6N_4$ requires N, 12.2 %).

2-Formyl-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-6-methoxycoumarone.—Equimolecular quantities of 6-methoxy-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumarone, dimethylformamide and phosphorus oxychloride were heated on the water-bath for 1 hour. The mixture was cooled, decomposed with water and warmed with an excess of 10% alkali. The crystalline product (yield 85%) was recrystallised from alcohol and obtained in colorless needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 137°.

2-Acetyl-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-6-methoxycoumarone.—6-Methoxy-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumarone was acetylated in carbon disulphide solution with equimolecular quantities of acetyl chloride and stannic chloride at 0°. The dark green complex was decomposed after 3 hours and the acetyl derivative isolated in quantitative yield, m.p. and mixed m.p. 155-56°. (Found: C, 70.4; H, 6.2. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{20}O_8$: C, 70.6; H, 5.9%). Similarly, by employing propionyl chloride, a moderate yield of 2-propionyl-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-6-methoxycoumarone, m.p. and mixed m.p. 170°, was obtained.

2-Benzoyl-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-6-methoxycoumarone was similarly prepared as above and obtained in colorless plates, m.p. 156° after crystallisation from alcohol and then acetic acid. (Found: C, 74.1; H, 5.3. $C_{28}H_{22}O_8$ requires C, 74.6; H, 5.5 %). The compound developed a yellow coloration with sulphuric acid. The 2-phenylacetyl derivative was obtained in poor yield and crystallised from alcohol in a crystalline mass, m.p. 214° (with prolonged sintering). (Found: C, 75.0; H, 5.3. $C_{26}H_{24}O_8$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.8 %).

Methyl 6-methoxy-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumarone-2-carboxylate was prepared in a quantitative yield from the corresponding acid by esterifying an ethereal suspension of the acid with excess of diazomethane. The ester crystallised from alcohol in colorless prisms, m.p. 142.5-143°. (Found: C, 67.5; H, 5.6. $C_{26}H_{30}O_8$ requires C, 67.4; H, 5.6 %).

Methyl 6-Methoxy-3-(6-nitro-3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumarone-2-carboxylate.—The foregoing ester (0.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (15 c.c.) and treated with concentrated nitric acid (0.6 c.c.) at the room temperature. The solution turned slightly yellow and soon pale yellow crystals of the nitro compound (0.5 g.) began to separate. Crystallised from acetic acid, the nitro compound was obtained in nearly colorless needles, m.p. 205°. (Found: C, 60.0; H, 5.1; N, 3.8. $C_{20}H_{18}O_8N$ requires C, 59.9; H, 4.7; N, 3.5 %).

Hydrolysis.—The ester was hydrolysed by boiling an alcoholic suspension with sodium hydroxide solution (5%) till complete solution (10 minutes). After removing alcohol, the mixture was diluted with water, acidified and the pale yellow crystalline mass (yield 70%) recrystallised from acetic acid and obtained in micro-crystalline powder, m.p. 247° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.0. $C_{19}H_{17}O_8N$ requires N, 4.8 %).

Decarboxylation.—The above nitro-acid (4 g.) was boiled with a mixture of quinoline (25 c.c.) and copper-bronze (1 g.) for 10 minutes. The mixture was cooled, acidified, extracted with ether and the ether solution washed with dilute alkali. *6-Methoxy-3-(6-nitro-3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumarone* was obtained in pale yellow needles (1.3 g.), m.p. 100° from methanol, showing a pink reaction with sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{17}O_8N$ requires C, 63.0; H, 5.0 %).

The Lactam (X).—The above nitro-acid (0.15 g.) was dissolved in ammonia (conc., 3 c.c.) and then a solution of ferrous sulphate (1.0 g.) in water was added and the mixture heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. Alkali (2 c.c., 10%) was added and the mixture boiled, filtered and acidified. The crude colorless amino-acid was collected, dried on the porous plate and boiled with acetic anhydride (1 c.c.) for a few minutes. The insoluble lactam separated soon, which was collected, washed with dilute alkali and then with alcohol, m.p. > 290°. (Found: N, 3.7. $C_{18}H_{17}O_8N$ requires N, 4.1 %).

Attempted Synthesis of ψ -Trimethylbrazilone.—The foregoing nitro compound (VII:R = NO₂; R' = H) (1.2 g.) in alcohol (8 c.c.) was boiled under reflux with stannous chloride (3 g.) and a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 2 hours. Alcohol was then removed and the residue boiled with water, tin precipitated with hydrogen sulphide, filtered hot and concentrated. The hydrochloride of the amine (VII:R = NH₂; R' = H) was obtained as a thick syrup which slowly solidified to long colorless pointed needles, giving a bluish green colour with sulphuric acid. The solution of this hydrochloride in dilute hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) was diazotised at the room temperature when a large quantity of a yellowish fluffy material, containing nitrogen, separated from which the diazonium salt was filtered (scarlet dye with alkaline β -naphthol) and added to cuprous cyanide solution (KCN 1.1 g., water 7 c.c., copper sulphate 1.0 g.). The yellow product that separated was filtered, dried, extracted with alcohol and concentrated, when the corresponding cyano compound was obtained as a gum, developing with sulphuric acid a pink colour, turning green. The compound did not crystallise. On hydrolysis with alcoholic potash for 24 hours (till the evolution of ammonia was complete), this cyano compound gave a trace of crystalline acidic

material, presumably (VII:R = COOH; R' = H), was obtained. The quantity was too meagre to permit isolation and identification.

Acylation of Methyl 6-Methoxy-3-(3:4-dimethoxybenzyl)-coumarone-2-carboxylate.—A solution of the ester (0.4 g.) in nitrobenzene (4 c.c.) was cooled to 0° and treated with acetyl chloride (0.2 g.) and stannic chloride (0.8 g.), and the resulting deep blue complex left in the cold for 24 hours. The mixture was decomposed with iced hydrochloric acid, nitrobenzene removed by steam-distillation and the gummy residue hydrolysed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide and the solution acidified. The voluminous jelly-like precipitate became granular on warming. This was collected; it gave a deep red colour with sulphuric acid, turning to bluish red. This acid was heated in a test tube in a metal bath till the evolution of carbon dioxide was over and the material was taken up in benzene and chromatographed on an alumina column. The violet fluorescing column was eluted with benzene and gave on evaporation a crystalline material (0.08 g.), m.p. 241°, identical with 3:8:9-trimethoxy-6-methyl- β -brazan. (Found: C, 74.2; H, 5.8. Calc. for C₂₆H₁₈O₄: C, 74.5; H, 5.6%).

3:8:9-Trimethoxy-6-ethyl- β -brazan was similarly prepared by employing propionyl chloride. The compound was obtained from pyridine in needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 154-55°.

Formylation of the ester with *N*-methylformanilide or dimethylformamide did not give encouraging result.

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